

Effect of elevated ultraviolet-B radiation on abscisic acid and indoleacetic acid content of rice leaves

Jinyu Zhang, Shaobai Huang, and Qiuji Dai, Jiangsu Academy of Agricultural Sciences, Nanjing 210014, China; S. Peng and B. S. Vergara, IRRRI

The effects of elevated UV-B (290-320 nm) radiation on plant growth and development have been reported in many plant species (Tevini 1993). Plant height and leaf area are the growth parameters most significantly affected (Barnes et al 1993, Dai et al 1992, Teramura et al 1991). Few studies have been conducted, however, on the mechanisms by which these parameters are influenced by UV-B.

Plant growth and development are closely related to the concentration of some endogenous growth regulators, such as abscisic acid (ABA) and indoleacetic acid (IAA). It is possible that morphological changes induced by enhanced UV-B radiation could be because of its effect on ABA and IAA content. The objectives of this study were to determine the effect of elevated UV-B radiation on the ABA and IAA content of rice leaves and to identify the possible mechanism by which plant height and leaf area are altered by UV-B.

Pregerminated seeds of rice cultivars IR74 and Naizersail were sown in 1-liter plastic pots, each containing 1.7 kg of Maahas clay soil fertilized with 3 g N, 1 g P, and 1 g K. Plants were grown in the greenhouse for 10 d and then subjected to various levels of UV-B radiation for up to 4 wk in a temperature- and humidity-controlled glasshouse (day/night temperature = 27/21 °C; RH = 70%). Photosynthetic photon flux at the top of the rice canopy under UV-B lamps at solar noon on a clear day was about 940 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2$ per s. UV-emitting fluorescent lamps supplied the UV-B radiation. Four levels of UV-B were imposed: 0.0, 6.0, 13.0, and 19.1 kJ/m^2 per d (weighted according to the general plant-action spectrum and normalized to unity at 300 nm). ABA content was determined by the method of Ross et al (1987) and IAA by the procedure of Weiler et al (1981) at the end of each treatment period.

No difference in ABA content was observed in IR74 under various levels of UV-B treatment for 2 wk, except under 19.1 kJ/m^2 per d. Naizersail showed a slight increase in ABA content under treatments of 13.0 and 19.1 kJ/m^2 per d (Fig. 1a). ABA production was stimulated significantly, however, by 4 wk of UV-B treatment (Fig. 1b). Under 2 wk of UV-B treatment, the amount of IAA in Naizersail was stable at 0.0, 6.0, and 13.0 kJ/m^2 per d of UV-B but declined significantly under 19.1 kJ/m^2 per d. IAA in IR74 decreased under 6.0, 13.0, and 19.1 kJ/m^2 per d of UV-B compared with no UV-B treatment (Fig. 1c). IAA content of IR74 and Naizersail was reduced significantly by 4 wk of exposure to higher UV-B levels (Fig. 1d).

Dramatic effects of enhanced UV-B radiation on plant morphology have been documented (Branes et al 1993, Dai et al

ABA and IAA contents of rice plants subjected to various levels of UV-B radiation.

1992, Tevini 1993). Our results indicate that enhanced UV-B radiation had a significant effect on ABA and IAA content of rice leaves after 4 wk of UV-B treatment. Production of ABA was stimulated while IAA content was decreased. ABA synthesis under stress conditions has been reported in several crops. It is not clear whether this decrease in IAA content under UV-B treatment was due to lower synthesis or to fast degradation. This study showed that ABA content is negatively related to plant height and leaf area while IAA content is positively associated with these two growth parameters (data not shown).

Tevini (1993) reported that morphological changes in sunflower seedlings

induced by UV-B radiation was the result of UV-dependent destruction of IAA and the formation of growth-inhibiting IAA photoproducts. Similarly, the growth response of rice plants to elevated UV-B radiation may be associated with the changes in endogenous concentrations of IAA and ABA in UV-B treated plants.

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Risk analysis of rice leaf blast epidemics associated with effects of enhanced ultra-violet-B and temperature changes in the Philippines

Y. Luo, D. O. TeBeest, Department of Plant Pathology, University of Arkansas, Fayetteville, Arkansas 72701, USA, P. S. Teng, and N. G. Fabellar, IRRI

Climatic variation and pests, of which rice blast is among the most important, greatly influence rice production in the tropics. The risk of blast epidemics caused by global climate changes is important to consider when developing disease control strategies. Previous work at IRRI has shown that lower temperatures in the tropics promote severe blast and highest yield loss and that elevated UV-B radiation causes more lesions, faster lesion expansion, and reduced spore viability. UV-B effects on rice growth and blast are therefore available for integrating into models to simulate blast epidemics and rice yield.

The objectives of this study were to incorporate UV-B effects into the RICE-BLAST model, and to simulate blast epidemics in the Philippines under a range of temperatures combined with elevated UV-B effects. Risk assessment was based on simulation results.

Model modification. A combination model, RICE-BLAST, was developed from the CERES-RICE model coupled to the BLASTSIM model and used to simulate rice blast epidemics based on rice growth and blast infection on leaves. Relative ratios of lesion number, lesion area expansion rate, and sporulation rate under UV-B exposure were coupled into corresponding subroutines by changing corresponding rates in blast infection. New external data files containing ratios

of effects of UV-B on components were developed. Variety IR30 was simulated under nonlimited water and nitrogen conditions. Estimated weather data under a normal year in Solana, Philippines, were used to simulate rice growth in the first growing season (Jan-May). UV-B effects on rice growth were quantified as a) reduction of net assimilation rate (decrease of dry weight and growth rate of leaf, stem, root, and grain caused by UV-B are the results from this reduction) and b) growth rate reduction for each component, such as reduction of dry weight accumulation rate of leaf, stem, root, and grain.

Two different coupling approaches using four components—leaf area, leaf, stem, and root dry weight—were tested: single coupling, in which only assimilation rate was considered, and multiple coupling, in which components including growth rates of root, leaf, and stem, were considered. We determined that single coupling is better than multiple coupling to simulate UV-B effects on rice growth; UV-B effects on leaf area predicted by multiple coupling is greater than that of observations; single coupling routine is to make the model more explanatory of the effects of UV-B on rice growth; and it is reasonable to use the modified model to simulate blast epidemics occurring under UV-B effects.

Parameter estimation. The relative ratios of UV-R treatments compared with controls were calculated from growth and physiological parameters of rice varieties IR30 and IR74 as affected by 4 wk of UV-B treatment (Q. Daj, IRRI, unpubl. data) and from the effects of UV-B on blast lesion number and lesion size under enhanced UV-B treatment and control on two UV-B-sensitive varieties, IR30 and IR72, infected with blast isolate PO6-6 (Finckh 1993).

Lesion expansion rate was estimated by $r = 1/t \cdot \log(L2/L1)$, where r is lesion expansion rate; $L1$ and $L2$ are lesion sizes, in mm^2 , at beginning date of lesion appearance and observation date, respectively; and t is number of days between date of lesion appearance and observation. $L1$ is assumed to be 5 mm^2 and t is 5 d. $L2$ was obtained from experimental data.

Relative ratio of lesion expansion (RRL) can be calculated from $RRL = rt/rc$, where R is lesion expansion rate under UV-B treatment and rc is lesion expansion rate under no UV-B control. Effect of UV-B on lesion number can be considered as similar to its effect on infection efficiency. Relative ratio of infection efficiency for the two varieties was calculated by lesion number under UV-B treatment divided by that of no UV-B control. Data of UV-B effect on sporulation were from unpublished data (Leung, Washington State University).

Simulation of global change effects. Thirty years of estimated weather data from seven Philippine locations, produced using either of two programs—WGEN or WMARK—were used in the simulations. Global temperature change treatments were considered by changing the estimated daily temperature data by +3, +1, 0, -1, and -3 °C. Three growing seasons for each location were separately simulated. In each growing season of each simulation year under each temperature change level, four situations were simulated: no blast without UV-B, blast without UV-R, no blast with UV-B, and blast with UV-B. Estimated yield, simulated area under the disease progress curve (AUDPC), and maximum severity of blast were produced at the end of each simulation run. AUDPC and maximum severity caused by blast without UV-B were compared with that caused by blast with UV-B effects. A risk scenario